

Home Based Physical Exercise for Prevention and Management of COVID-19 Pandemic and for its Associated Consequences

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Received date: February 15, 2021; Accepted date: March 01, 2021; Published date: March 08, 2021

Citation: Teferi G (2021) Home Based Physical Exercise for Prevention and Management of COVID-19 Pandemic and for its Associated Consequences. Glob J Res Rev Vol.8 No.2: 62.

Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic has forced many of us round the world to remain reception and self-isolate for a long period of time. These leads to psychological outcomes such as depression, post-traumatic stress symptoms, panic, confusion, anger, fear, and substance misuse and develops Sedentary Death Syndrome and reduce individuals' functional ability. But at this time if an individual follows a physically active lifestyle or participate regularly in home based physical activity, it has been found to be an effective way of improving fitness and overall health of individual. The effect of regular home based exercise training has a significant positive effect on overall health of individuals. The World Health Organization (WHO) has recommended clear guidelines on the minimal amount of physical activity necessary to maintain health and fitness. Based on age categories, 60 min per day of moderate-to-vigorous physical activity for 6-17-yr-olds, and 75 min per week of vigorous or 150 min per week of moderate physical activity for adults and elderly, including 3 and 2 days per week, respectively, with muscle and bone strengthening. Generally, mental and physical well-being are negatively affected by sedentary habits of physical activity and positively affected by active lifestyle (regular physical activity).

Keywords: Home-based physical activity; COVID-19; Physical inactivity; P andemic

Introduction

Corona viruses are sort of viruses that are phenotypically and genotypically diverse. The outbreak of COVID-19 starts in December 2019 in Wuhan, China. As of 17 March 2020, the widespread human-to-human transmission now had resulted over 19 million people infected. Because the COVID-19 pandemic continues to develop in most countries and various prevention strategies are introduced by the govt of just about all countries, including the closing of faculties and universities, and bans on travel, cultural and sporting events, and social gatherings. People are ordered or advised to remain reception, and a number of other countries have requested all returning travelers to self-isolate for a fourth-night of these actions are considered as an effective measures for preventing the virus

spreading and for managing those that do contract the virus. But these actions will negatively affect people's physical activity habits, with longer spent by sitting and watching screens and a subsequent impact on physical health, well-being, sleeping patterns and quality of life. The beneficial effects of normal workout on many health outcomes are well established. Different research has demonstrated specific benefits like improved physical and physiological health parameters and positive health outcomes in areas of psychological state and wellbeing. For these reasons, implementing home based physical activity programme during the amount of the pandemic will reduce the negative physiological and psychological state impact of sedentary behaviors. According to the regulations recently set by the Ethiopian government, for instance, it's mandated that each one peoples must remain reception unless required to maneuver for valid reasons, like work, health or for other unavoidable issues like assisting those that are sick or disabled, or purchasing groceries and medications. All sporting activities and competitions are cancelled. However, one important exception has been made to permit people to practice sports and outdoor physical activity, as long as an interpersonal distance of a minimum of 1 m might be maintained. "Sedentary Death Syndrome" If, in fact, quarantine experience increases can cause psychological problems like depression, post-traumatic stress symptoms, panic, confusion, anger, fear, and substance misuse, it also can give the thanks to several patho-physiological mechanisms arising from inactivity. Physical inactivity are often defined because the range of situations that, thanks to impossibility of movement (paralysis) or personal habit (long sitting hours), produce decreased energy expenditure toward basal level. It's important to understand that pathologies or worsening of medical conditions caused by inactivity often show their symptoms and manifestations over the future, and are usually pre-clinically silent. it's estimated that physical inactivity is responsible, worldwide, for between 6% and 10% of non-communicable disease, including, among others, paralysis, strokes, heart diseases, cancers, diabetes, chronic renal disorder, osteoarthritis, osteoporosis, Alzheimer's disease and Parkinson's disease. Physical inactivity also increases the loss of functional abilities with aging, resulting in decreases in anticipation, with impacts potentially as large as renowned risk factors like smoking and obesity. The term "sedentary death syndrome" was first wont to give attention to the present alarming problem, warning about the risks related to the imbalance between calorie intake and output, which may cause

hyperinsulinemia and thus adiposity. Overweight, or worse, obesity, are largely related to an increased risk of cardiovascular problems, osteoporosis, osteoarthritis muscle wasting, and overall physical and mental distress shown in **Figure 1**

Figure 1: Mental and physical well-being are negatively affected by sedentary habits and positively affected by active lifestyle.

In this context, physical activity doesn't only represent a crucial part of disease prevention but also drugs for inactivity-associated disorders. Physical activity represents a non-pharmacological approach for promoting general health [1-8].

Recommendations on Physical Activity

The World Health Organization (WHO) has suggested clear guidelines on the minimal amount of physical activity necessary to take care of health. For instance, it recommends that adults aged between 18 and 64 years, the age bracket most suffering from COVID-19 consistent with recent statistics (i.e. accounting for over 70% of all severe cases), should engage in weekly training of a minimum of 150 min of moderate-intensity physical activity or 75 min of vigorous-intensity physical activity, or a corresponding combination of moderate- and vigorous-intensity activity. Current evidences also support the benefits of normal physical activity on survival. Physical Activity and psychological state Obesity and overweight rates among all groups in society, no matter age, sex, race, socioeconomic status, educational level, or geographical area have noticeably increased within the last twenty years. Obesity and overweight aren't just a private matter; it's also public health epidemics that affects education achievement outcomes, economic productivity, state budgets and successively affect students' academic achievement. Additionally to disease prevention, studies suggest that physical activity directly benefits cognition and academic achievement. In one study, during which children jogged for thirty minutes two to fourfold per week, researchers measured a rise in activity within the prefrontal cortex, suggesting greater cognitive function. However, the cognitive gains were only sustained while children maintained the jogging regimen. If a private follows a physically active lifestyle, it's been found to be an efficient way of improving fitness and overall health. Conversely, the absence of a physically active lifestyle can adversely affect health and well-being, increasing the danger of somatic health problems like cardiovascular diseases, hypertension, DM, osteoporosis, and a few sorts of cancer. Additionally, regular PA is understood to possess a positive impact on psychological state. Variety of meta-analyses of

intervention studies of the effect of exercise training have revealed that exercise may have a big moderate to high anti-depressive effect. In other way if students have poor fitness different problems are appearing additionally to academic achievement problems like apnea, which has been linked to problems with learning and memory, liver problems, orthopedic problems and asthma. If there's apnea problem in children, it can to impair a child's ability to concentrate and stay alert during the day, which could have a negative impact on academic performance also reported, supported their study results, being physically fit reduces the danger of disorder, carcinoma, diabetes, dying prematurely, and obesity. Increased physical activity levels and fitness can improve bone and musculoskeletal function and help alleviate or relieve depression, anxiety and stress (mental health). Generally the previous research findings from large-scale observational studies indicated that participation in physical activity features a small to moderate effect in prevention and management of the danger of depression and anxiety which successively have effect on academic achievement and psychological state. Reductions in physical activity can also affect one's psychological state, which can be experienced as unpleasant emotions like sadness, anger, frustration and/or irritation. During a review on psychological impact of quarantine recently performed by Brooks et al., the authors stated that experiencing disease outbreaks can trigger symptoms of post-traumatic stress, depression and/or confusion among others. During quarantine, staying active and maintaining a workout routine is going to be essential for mental and physical health. Fortunately, a good range of exercises, like video-or app-guided equipment-free aerobics or strength training, are often performed reception and will be encouraged. We hence encourage national, federal and region al governments round the world to incorporate clear exceptions for physical activity in nationwide lockdowns. These should also leave safe performance of outside physical activities (e.g. walking, running or other individual sports, where an adequate interpersonal distance are often maintained). consistent with are often concluded that workout are often beneficial for the defenses of the entire body and should be counted among preventative measures against the results of tract virus infection, that, on the opposite hand, sedentary habits might be related to increased risk of predisposition to infections [9-12].

Impact of COVID-19 and Physical Inactivity on the Immune System

SARS-CoV-2 may results corona virus disease (COVID-19) shows the major symptoms of ever, dry cough, myalgia, and fatigue. Currently, there are neither vaccines nor clinically proven effective medicines. Convalescent plasma and anti-viral drugs have shown some hopes in treating COVID-19 patients, but their widespread use await statistical rigor. Currently the best and only measures to reduce the spread, morbidity and mortality are social distancing and hygiene. As this virus strain is novel to the human immune system, we are dependent on aspects of our innate resistance to deal with the first infection. Like other viral infections, if we resist the infection, over the course of weeks we can develop antibody and cell-mediated

immune responses specific to the virus. In most instances, this exposure-related 'training' of our immune systems offers us long-lasting protection from re-infection or, if we are re-infected, disease symptoms are much milder.

Physical activity affects the immune system and its anti-viral defenses positively. Animal experiments administering influenza and herpes simplex viruses 1 (HSV-1) in the respiratory tract, have revealed that moderate exercise, performed before (i.e. training) or after infection (for a few days before symptom onset), improves morbidity and mortality to the infection. In other way, preclinical studies have also shown that intense exercise leads to poorer outcomes in response to respiratory viral infections. Follow-up research findings have concluded on some understanding of the mechanisms responsible for these observations [13-16].

The current epidemiological study has showed that intense, prolonged exercise was correlated with an increase in upper respiratory tract infections. This work leads to the concept of the inverted J theory, where moderate intensity of exercise reduces, and prolonged, high intensity exercise increases susceptibility to infection. Many research findings have supported the theory with respect to individual immune parameters including those specific to viral defense. For example, salivary lactoferrin and its secretion rate increased for up to 2 hours after moderate intensity of physical exercise. Mucosal lactoferrin is very important because it can protect DNA and RNA viruses from infecting cells by binding and blocking host receptors. In other way, low levels or secretion rates of salivary immunoglobulin A, which can bind to viruses and inactivate them, has been shown to be associated with upper respiratory tract infection in some individuals who undergoing intense physical exercise training. In addition, because physical exercise leads to profound movement of leukocytes in blood and tissues, many researchers conclude that being physically active increases immune surveillance against infectious pathogens including viruses.

COVID-19, Physical Activity, and the Respiratory System

While the clinical research of the COVID-19 pandemic continues to be investigated, many COVID-19 patients develop respiratory failure and require mechanical ventilation (MV) to maintain adequate pulmonary gas exchange. In this regard, a recent report reveals that ~54% of patients hospitalized thanks to COVID-19 experience respiratory failure and >30% require MV. Although MV is usually a life-saving intervention, an unwanted consequence of prolonged MV is that the rapid development of respiratory muscle weakness thanks to diaphragm muscle atrophy and contractile dysfunction (collectively termed ventilator-induced diaphragm dysfunction, VIDD). VIDD is clinically significant because diaphragmatic weakness may be a major contributor to the lack to wean patients from the ventilator. Many COVID-19 patients often require prolonged time on the ventilator that increases the danger of weaning problems. Patients who experience difficult weaning suffer higher morbidity and mortality than patients weaned quickly on their first attempts to break away the

ventilator and unfortunately, many COVID-19 patients succumb to ICU-related complications. As long as respiratory muscle weakness may be a primary risk factor for failure to wean from the ventilator, developing strategies to guard the diaphragm against MV-induced weakness has become a priority in critical care medicine. Interestingly, different studies have showed positive impact of endurance exercise training on the system respiratorium has led the way. Although many organ systems adapt in response to endurance exercise training, the structural and functional properties of the lung and airways aren't altered thanks to exercise training. Specifically, endurance exercise training promotes numerous biochemical alterations in diaphragm muscle leading to a phenotype that's protected against several challenges including prolonged MV. Indeed, as few as 10 consecutive days of endurance exercise training leads to significant protection against VIDD. Therefore, it's predicted that endurance trained individuals that develop COVID-19 and need ventilator support will enjoy the exercise-induced preconditioning of the diaphragm.

PA and Exercise Programming During a Pandemic

The effect of regular physical exercise on non-communicable and also have positive impact on the immune system and modern lifestyle behaviors promote physical inactivity which leads peoples become sedentary. These poor lifestyle behaviors are intensified by social distancing and self-imposed or authorities mandated quarantine measures intended to reduce COVID-19 spread. These circumstances pose significant challenges for remaining physically active. During times of isolation, all socioeconomic groups, ethnicities, and ages should maintain healthiness by following the WHO PA recommendations of 150 minutes of moderate-intensity or 75 minutes of vigorous-intensity PA per week, or a mixture of both. Muscle-strengthening activities involving major muscle groups are recommended on two or more days per week. In children/adolescents the recommendations include at least 60 minutes per day of vigorous or moderate intensity PA.

Starting an exercise program during a pandemic

When starting physical exercise program while in the midst of pandemic, public health recommendations for social distancing and hygiene practices should be considered. Becoming physically active and reducing sedentary behavior is definitely accomplished by avoiding sitting for while periods, taking short movement or activity breaks, utilizing online exercise classes, and using mobile technologies like telephone applications and wearable sensors to encourage movement. A goal of any beginning PA or exercise program is to progressively work toward completing a minimum of one-half hour of moderate PA a day or a minimum of twenty minutes of vigorous PA every other day of the week. Ideally, strengthening-type activities are included in daily activities a minimum of twice every week. Individuals have chronic diseases like cardiovascular or pulmonary disease should seek advice from health care

providers regarding safe exercises. Recommendations for youngsters and youth aged five to 17 years are the buildup of a minimum of hour of moderate - to vigorous-intensity daily PA. Additionally, vigorous-intensity physical activities that strengthen muscle and bone are recommended a minimum of three times per week. If engaged in regular workout and eager to further enhance cardiovascular and muscle fitness, suddenly beginning an intense aerobic and resistance exercise educational program or performing unaccustomed highly intense prolonged exercise isn't prudent, because such PA or exercise training can cause reduced immune function.

Recommended Home-based and individualized Physical Activity

There is likely to be very limited opportunity to practice physical activity outside home during this pandemic period, with most of the people advised to remain reception to stop transmission of the virus. it's thus recommended that folks should stay active by exercising at their home. For this purpose promoting physical activity is extremely important, multiple exercise modes are often applied, including aerobics using stationary bikes or rowing ergo meters, weight strength training, dance-based exercise and active gaming. For youngsters and youth (5-17 yrs), WHO recommends 60 min of daily physical activity with moderate to vigorous aerobic intensity, with muscle and bone strengthening three days per week. For adults and elderly (>17 yrs), recommend physical activity for 75 min/wk with vigorous aerobics intensity or 150 min/wk of moderate aerobic intensity, with muscle and bone strengthening two days per week. The aerobics training types are described in below for trained and untrained individuals, with the specific intensity associated with pulse, rating of perceived exertion (RPE) also as intensity with regard to the degree of breathlessness during exercise. Dancing activities reception, audio-visual-directed gymnastics and aerobics are often recommended for maintenance of cardiovascular, metabolic and musculoskeletal fitness and for reducing the severity of symptoms of depression and anxiety. Dance-based workout involves the utilization of body movements which helps to enhance.

Conclusion

Generally, home- based regular physical exercise program can provide an opportunity for people to stay physically healthy by practicing simple movements with low-moderate to high intensity in the time of staying at home. The best way to overcome Covid-19 associated problems is to substitute outdoors regular exercise program with home- based/ individualized/ regular exercise program, such as bodyweight training and dance-based aerobic exercise, and if possible, aerobic high-intensity exercise using different machines, also with self paced protocols. These physical exercises can be combined with, but not substituted by, stretching and active gaming. The great importance of a healthy diet during this pandemic period also should give more attention. Generally, maintaining a regular physical activity raining, carefully in a park

setting or safely at home, is a helpful strategy to reduce the consequences of this pandemic, both at the physical and mental level. The time spent at home could therefore be changed into by participating mostly in home based aerobic exercise to build a positive and mindful relationship with the long-term health benefits of exercising.

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